

Integration of Sustainable Development Goals into the Educational Setting

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Abstract

Developing values is an integral part of growing up. Schools are part of the community where young people learn their ethical framework for life. The UN 2030 Agenda and its Sustainable Development Goals are growing in importance (United Nations, 2020). Many countries are committed to being a partner in integrating the SDGs and bringing them into action. Part of that is the structured implementation in schools. The aim of this article is to give an example on how Education for Sustainable Development can be implemented in a school and to examine how these practices may influence social behavior, and promote the care for others and nature.

Keywords: *Education for sustainable development, value development, citizenship education, Adolescents, curriculum, global goals, sustainability*

Introduction

Around the world, the awareness of people of sustainable practices is growing. Part of this movement is the gaining importance of the *United Nations Sustainable Development Goals* (SDGs or Global Goals). Political leaders worldwide have committed their nations to sustainable policies and practices to become active promoters of the Global Goals (United Nations, 2020).

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) fosters sustainability competencies in school. ESD approaches focus on including environmental and social issues in educational programs. ESD educators are also concerned with transforming behavior of students to develop knowledge, skills, and values to foster sustainable development (UNESCO, 2019). Promoting change-making for sustainable development in the educational setting needs to include not only knowledge transfer but also the strengthening of skills to have a positive influence on the status quo. Ideally, school personnel support young people to grow into content, responsible, and socially competent adults. Including ESD in the curriculum could aid this endeavor. In this paper, ESD will be used to develop structures for simplified integration of the Global Goals into the curriculum. The framework is to assist educators in helping guide students to become global citizens caring about one another and the world.

Significance

Today's global society has myriad challenges such as inequalities, climate change, resource scarcity, and pandemics which the United Nations Agenda 2030 can help address. The aim is to create a more resilient and fairer society with all stakeholders working together. Understanding the possible influences of ESD on youth development gives opportunities for the next step in developing an evidence-based systematic implementation of educational practices in school.

The *United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization* (UNESCO) developed a framework for implementing the 17 Global Goals in school settings to promote justice and sustainability. This

framework is the basis of the program Education for Sustainable Development: Realizing the Global Sustainable Development Goals (ESD 2030). The UN Global Goals provide pillars for coping with economic, ecological, and social challenges in the world.

Students need to learn the necessary knowledge and tools for critical analysis of environmental and social issues and learn about options for action. The integration of the Global Goals can support students to develop an understanding and want to care for each other and the environment. Within the ESD program, initiatives of learning projects promote the active engagement of stakeholders in solving real-world issues. The engagement leads to self-reflection of part-takers and an evaluation of society's actions and behaviors, leading to new knowledge, skills, and values.

Stakeholders of ESD are teachers, staff, students, administrators, parents, and other community members. The main focus of the program is on student learning. Schools with a systematic whole institution approach to foster authentic ESD learning can aid youth competence in their transformative potential and help the Global Goals to become part of society. Teachers and other stakeholders (e.g. community partnerships) provide learning opportunities for students to engage in. Students develop self-motivation to further pursue their area of interest and take charge of their learning while engaging in service-oriented projects. Through promoting the Global Goals, the learning community contributes to a more sustainable and just society and world.

The author worked in a K-12 school in Germany in a socio-economic challenged area. The school has disproportionately high numbers of pupils with a migrant background and associated disadvantages such as poverty, unemployment and health issues. The pupils are from over 80 different countries. Therefore, cultural, ethnic, and racial diversity is immense in the student population. Decisions on program implementations have to be oriented on the people involved. The evaluation process as well as the communication of its findings needs to be connected to the students' cultural diversity. Studies suggest that ESD practices teach students about our environment and help them develop life-skills such as leadership, collaboration, and critical thinking. However, ESD is also linked to the inclusion of marginalized groups and perspectives (Wals & Kieft, 2010). Given the specific circumstances in the setting, the implementation of ESD was especially relevant. The school in focus is just implementing ESD.

The evaluation of the program from the very start is critical to ensure that the project leaders can make necessary adjustments and next steps can be identified early on.

Objectives

Objectives can help the successful implementation of the program to ensure student engagement and program effectiveness. The defined aims of the program are promoting knowledge among students and all stakeholders about the Global Goals, fostering understanding of the interrelatedness of Goals, to learn system thinking approaches, and motivate informed action to achieve the Goals. These objectives need to be well defined within the structure of the setting to be achievable. These are the defined objectives for the school in focus:

- IF ESD is part of the school, THEN the students develop knowledge and new understandings of sustainable development.
- IF the students know social and environmental issues, THEN they develop an understanding and want to care for each other and the environment.
- IF the students learn to care about changing pressing issues, THEN they can reflect on their own and society's actions to develop new skills and behaviors.
- IF the students can find sustainable and supportive ways to act, THEN they can change their habits and become life-long positive change-makers.
- IF Educators and students embody positive change-maker qualities, THEN they can inspire others to make sustainable choices, and the program can have a broader community impact.
- IF school leaders implement the ESD program, THEN they help prepare young people for global, sustainable development challenges.

Method

The inclusion of Global Goals into the curriculum happens in a service-learning set-up. The SDGs are part of lessons and become closely linked to subject-specific learning. Students should gain an understanding of the Agenda 2030 – the depth will need to be defined to meet the specific educational circumstances and needs of the students. The overarching idea of this approach is for students to become positive changemakers. Therefore, student inquiry and agency are actively fostered. The learning needs to be based on authentic needs. While actual change in the world is encouraged, the main focus remains on learning outcomes and the building of critical consciousness. The learning outcomes should be shared and demonstrated in some way - ideally publicly with community involvement. Oriented on other experts such as Root & Billig, Seifert et al. came up with six quality guidelines to define effective service-learning structures in an educational setting: Real need, Curricular connection; Reflection; Participation of students; Engagement outside of school; Recognition and graduation (2008). Student involvement and engagement are essential to give relevance to authentic issues that need investigation and problem-solving skills.

Evaluation

The following questions guide the program evaluation:

- How can staff and student buy-in for the program be promoted?
- How can students learn the necessary knowledge and tools for critical analysis and options for action?
- How can school personnel promote settings in which students reflect their own and society's actions and behaviors to develop new knowledge, skills, and values?
- What assessment methods can best determine the impact of ESD?
- What can we learn from challenges and results?

The first area of the evaluation questions is concerned with structural questions as well as knowledge transmission and acquisition. Those are questions such as "How can students learn the necessary knowledge and tools for critical analysis and options for action?" For this first area of evaluation interest, the researcher can create transparent coding systems and quantitatively collect data—with standardization of the data collection on specific actions and outcomes. For example, systematically recording different teaching approaches and comparing them to the students' knowledge gain through standardized pre-and post-test tests. The other domain of guiding evaluation questions falls into a section of value development of youth. Those are questions such as "How can school personnel promote settings in which students reflect their own and society's actions and behaviors for value development?".

A different approach fits this second area of evaluation interest. Examining and evaluating the development of youth values and how they can influence choices and social behavior are complex concepts that require a deeper understanding of the individuals' motivations and driving forces. A qualitative research approach is needed to gain insights into these individual decision-making processes and is ideal for gathering data to gain understanding (Verstehen) (Firstone, 1987).

Essential in the communication with teachers is to highlight what is working and what can be built on. Studies show that teachers' knowledge, competencies, attitudes, and values considerably impact the implementation of ESD at schools (Rieckmann et al., 2017). It might be helpful to have some teachers share their experiences to create a cooperative community in the evaluation process. Available data (digital or in printed form) might aid in giving teachers a deeper understanding of the findings of the evaluation and the goals of the program.

When communicating findings with students, the focus could be better placed on examples of learning. This focus might create interest and a chance for students to express how they would like the program to precede. Evaluation is essential for improvement. The students need to have a say in

the evaluation process. The findings have to be seen and communicated within the cultural context of the evaluation (Yarbrough et al., 2011). These conversations can further inform the evaluation conclusions and help discover any misconceptions or biases. The evaluation process can not only gather data to justify the program but also create buy-in and excitement of teachers and students as their opinions are valued in how the program progresses.

The traditional approach to evaluation does not fit the demands of ESD as the approach has diverse learning outcomes that are difficult to grasp. The Cadwell Collaborative identified learning benefits of ESD such as ecological knowledge, the ability to think critically, systemically, and creatively, decision-making and problem-solving skills, empathy, commitment to social justice, inclusiveness and equity, effectively taking action, and ability to envision long term consequences (2021). These characteristics were considered to match competence development standards within the German curriculum. But "how does one measure empathy and tolerance? What is basic empathy? How does one measure proficiency in empathy?" (Ornstein & Hunkins, 2018, p.288). Hadjichambis & Paraskeva-Hadjichambi defined evaluation processes for the ESD implementation that helped create guiding assessment rubrics (2020).

Discussion

There is little guidance on how educators can create educational environments to promote positive values without imposing them. Seeking to analyze ESD practice and youth development's relationship creates research-grounded guidance on the effectiveness and value of fostering appreciation in the educational setting. Values are associated with various areas, such as attitudes, interests, preferences, and moral beliefs. Such complex concepts must be researched so that a deeper understanding of individual motivations and decision-making processes is gained.

A vision is essential for active change-making, and the importance of transforming the status quo and meeting the Global Goals is evident. More than two millennia ago, Heraclitus said, "the only constant in life is change" (Baird, 2010). This is still true today. Nevertheless, it still is a challenge to promote positive social transformation. Complex psychological and social structures determine phenomena of the physical world. Western societies generally measure success in terms of economic growth. Societies and individuals can get into unsustainable patterns with short-term rewards but unaffordable long-term costs (Costanza et al., 2020).

However, recent cultural trends demonstrate a shift in value. Instead of unreflected consumerism, buyers start to focus on ecological and social justice issues when purchasing goods. Instead of promoting excessive work as a badge of honor, there is a more vital call for well-being and self-care. ESD fosters this understanding and caring interactions with oneself, others, and the world.

Sometimes educators dread including service-learning approaches in their teaching as it may seem overwhelming on how to create connections. The truth is that the Global Goals are a great resource to guide educators to develop authentic learning experiences. The SDGs as context help give meaning to the learned knowledge, concepts, and skills in the curriculum.

Service-learning projects provide the students with immediate answers and authentic experiences of why their learning is vital for their life. All sustainable development goals are essentially geared to creating a sustainable future for everyone. Ideally, students internalize the service and global citizen values and grow into becoming life-long positive change-makers. Service-learning is not community service or community-based learning. It is categorized by specific attributes, such as its primary focus on learning outcomes. The educational aspects of the process are as important as the practical outcomes.

ESD promotes knowledge, skills, and abilities that help students become future-oriented in their thinking and acting: How do my decisions affect people in future generations or other parts of the world? What are the effects of what and how I consume? What consequences does my choice of transport have? Is it relevant how much energy I use? Which global mechanisms lead to conflict,

poverty, and war? ESD promotes an individual's understanding of the effects of their actions and choices on the world and enables them to make more conscious and responsible decisions (UNESCO, 2018). Integrating ESD aims to empower and motivate students to become conscious citizens who think critically and take action to create a better future for all.

The successful ESD application needs to incorporate experiential learning set-ups to promote participation and inclusion. The teaching needs to be learner-centered, action-oriented, and transformative (Waltner, Rieß, & Brock, 2018). Students are actively involved in change-making processes, practicing problem-solving skills, fostering awareness and empathy when they emerge in authentic knowledge learning activities. Fostering compassion, empathy, and solidarity among students is essential to prepare them for a good life in a globalized world.

Many of the problems we have to face today can only be solved together in the largest possible collective. Global challenges such as climate change require solidarity that extends far beyond national borders.

All curriculum developers had to define their idea of what education is for. Worldviews are the driving force in the choice of curriculum approaches. "Curriculum ideologies are defined as beliefs about what schools should teach, for what ends, and for what reasons" (Eisner, 2002).

ESD aligns with a humanistic ideology as it focuses on helping students develop self-awareness and inspire them to better society. The approach aligns with a curriculum aim to enhance self-actualization, self-determining learning processes, and human striving. Promoting critical consciousness and global citizenship reminds of humanist Maslow's statement that "a positive self image and healthy self esteem is based on approval, acceptance and recognition from others; but also upon actual accomplishments, achievements and success upon the realistic self confidence which ensues" (Ornstein & Hunkins, 2018, p.145).

The curriculum implementation has to involve creating structures, gathering relevant resources, and creating networks around ESD. Indicators and quality criteria need to be developed to evaluate the learning outcome of implemented programs. There needs to be a balance of structure and freedom, considering academic and social goals, and continuously re-evaluating all aspects of the design concept to ensure an optimal weighting of priorities.

Each unique project's scope - the specific themes and areas of content - will be defined by the educator planning the implementation. At the school in Germany, a focus group provided examples to give guidance on possible connections of curriculum topics and SDGs. Designed planning documents help structuring the sequences.

Personal choice goes hand in hand with fostering critical consciousness. Students' interests are essential to developing projects as they need to be the driving force for determining personally relevant learning experiences. Students' learning needs and preferences have to be considered when developing instructions. This focus speaks for a learner-centered curriculum design. However, cross-curricular learning and exposing students to real-life issues are at the heart of the authentic educational set-ups of ESD. Therefore, a problem-centered curriculum design founded on learner-centered values represents this approach best. Traditional curriculum approaches cannot keep up with the pace of modern society. These demands have to be met with a dynamic, conversational, and evolutionary curriculum focused on the learner. Students' needs are not static but always evolving.

In ESD, real-life issues are driving the curriculum. The aim is to create more equity and a better world for all. Injustice and discrimination are addressed and debated to find solutions.

Students are encouraged to envision a better world and care enough about realizing it to become active change-makers. Learning primarily occurs in cooperative group work through experiences and activities. The teacher is seen as a guide that helps students reflect on their experiences and supports real-life action, involvement, and inquiry. Specific project outcomes may be evident, but more important is the personal development of the student.

Conclusion

Almost one hundred years ago, Counts pointed out the pressure put on schools to reinvent society: "We are convinced that education is the one unfailing remedy for every ill to which man is subject, whether it be vice, crime, war, poverty, riches, injustice, racketeering, political corruption, race hatred, class conflict, or just plain original sin. We even speak glibly and often about the general reconstruction of society through the school." (1932, p. 3). These are utopian goals. However, schools are an environment that contributes to shaping students' view of and approach to life. Schools transmit ethics and principles even without meaning to. The question is if such value guidance in education will take place intentionally.

We need to encourage learning with a sense of independence. Modern educational ideas align with this approach. Training independence is especially relevant in today's fastly evolving society. Global trends, such as globalization, urbanization, automation, and digitization, have forever changed the world. Today's world challenges are too complex for simple solutions and need the joint commitment of political and economic actors as well as committed citizens.

Cooperation is at the heart of success. However, cooperation does not happen automatically. We need to come together to create a more unifying approach inviting all stakeholders to participate, exchange ideas, and become part of the change-making process. School should give young people the courage to find their own new ways of life in a continually changing world. They need to have a chance to explore how to shape society beyond the prescribed norms. Education could be understood as the ability to create utopias. Now and then. The article is supposed to help educators on implementing the SDGs in their curricular framework. The hope is that schools and educators gain confidence in implementing ESD approaches and connections to the SDGs. Essential is to empower students to lead ESD initiatives. There has to be a connection between what students learn in the classroom, the values that we promote and the opportunities for real life application. We need to be especially eager to find ways to serve our students in accomplishing their ideas and initiatives. Because in the end not the immediate change is the overarching measure of success but the instilled mindset in the youth.

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